

Factsheet

Progress of the NBS implementation and testing in the Netherlands

THE CONTEXT

The Dutch NBS site in trans4num has two locations where different nature-based solutions are being tested.

Ebelsheerd Location: On this site the winter wheat test fields are nearly harvested and the results will be processed to generate yield figures and crop observations. Construction for the 2025-2026 growing season is ongoing.

Kollumerwaard Location: On this site, the potato trial is in full swing, with observations continuing throughout the growing season.

Trials methodologies

- 1) **Conventional Winter Wheat Trial:** Different nitrogen application strategies are being tested with the Bennington variety to optimize fertilization for improved crop performance.
- 2) **Organic Winter Wheat Trial:** The Calgary variety is being used to compare the effects of organic inputs, including bio-fertilizers and organic amendments, on crop health and yield.
- 3) **Potato Trial Field:** The Fontane variety is being studied to evaluate the effectiveness of NBS in protecting seed potatoes from virus infections through aphid control.

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Stakeholder engagement

SPNA has organized meetings with farmers to discuss trial field results and practical applications of the research. A meeting was held at the Ebelsheerd site to discuss winter wheat trials, attracting around 50 attendees. At Kollumerwaard meetings focused on potato trial fields.

Preliminary findings

Soil and crop samples have been collected and analyzed to evaluate the impact of different crop rotations and fertilization strategies. Analyses include soil physical and chemical properties, as well as microbial community assessments.

Findings show distinct differences in nutrient content, soil structure, and microbial diversity across the fields, with notable variations between conventional and organic management practices.

Next steps

Initial results from the 2023 sampling and trials have been compiled and analyzed, demonstrating promising outcomes in terms of yield, soil health, and microbial diversity.

Findings have been documented in scientific articles and reports. A new cycle of trials for 2023-2024 has begun, building on the findings from the previous year and incorporating adjusted methodologies.

